

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Synthesis And Antimitotic Activity of Benzotriazole Compound

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 24 April. 2025

Keywords:

Benzotriazole Synthesis,
Antimitotic Method,
Diazotisation Reaction, Seed
Germination Assay.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15273474

ABSTRACT

The present work to Synthesize benzotriazole Nucleus and study the biological activity of Antimitotic method through by seed germination assay by using the green gram seeds. It is preliminary screening method to identify this benzotriazole basic nucleus is having Anticancer property. By using this seed germination assay method be can studied that this nucleus is having inhibition of seed germination Activity.

INTRODUCTION

Benzotriazole is Bicyclic heterocyclic compound with three nitrogen atoms in the five membered

ring i.e. triazole ring fused with benzene ring. This Pharmacophore molecule shows a wide Spectrum of pharmacological activities.

Table.1: Chemical Information of Benzotriazole [1-3]

Synonyms	1H-Benzotriazole, Benzotriazole,1,2,3-Benzotriazole
Chemical formula	C ₆ H ₅ N ₃
Molecular weight	119.12 g/mole
Chemical structure	
Density	1.36 g/ml
Melting point	100°c
Appearance	White solid
Chemical safety category	Environmental Hazard, Harmful

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Table.2: Materials used for the Reaction

Apparatus	Chemicals
Weighing balance	orthophenylene diamine
Glassine	Sodium Nitrite
Ice water bath	Glacial acetic acid
Thermometer	Distilled water
RFB	
Beaker	
Measuring cylinder	
Heating mantle	
Gravity filtration setup	
Desiccator	

Principle involved in the synthesis of Benzotriazole: [4-6]

The sodium nitrite reacts with glacial acetic acid and liberates nitrous acid. The o-phenylenediamine reacts with nitrous acid and produce diazonium ion. When the structure and stereochemistry of diazonium ion are stable, intramolecular nitrogen coupling occurs and forms benzotriazole.

Table.3: Procedure for the Preparation of the Reaction mixture:

Reaction mixture-1	Reaction mixture-2
Dissolve 1.3 grams of O-phenylenediamine in a mixture of 1.5 ml of glacial acetic acid and 5 ml water in a beaker. Stir until the solid dissolves, warm gently if necessary. Cool the solution to 15°C. Stir well	Add a solution of 2 grams of sodium nitrite in 2 ml water.

Table.4: Materials used for seed germination Assay method

Contents	Quantity
Green grams (Vigna radiata)	25 grams
Sigma-Aldrich Polystyrene petri dishes	5 petri dishes
Benzotriazole drug solution (BZT)	50 ml BZT
Vehicle used-Distilled water	50 ml

Mixing RM-1 & RM-2 then this resultant reaction mixture will become warm within 2-3 minutes and reaches a temperature of about 85°C. and then begin to cool. Colour changes from deep red to pale brown. Continue stirring for 15 minutes till the temperature fall about 35-40°C. Thoroughly chill in the ice bath for 30 minutes. Filter the product and wash with cold water. Product is dried under Desiccator.

Evaluation of Antimitotic activity of Benzotriazole compound [7-12]

Seed germination Assay Method:

Green gram seeds were purchased from the market and stored in a moisture free place in self-sealing cover. Then accurately weighed 5 grams of seeds and incorporated in each and every sigma-Aldrich polystyrene petri dishes to study the antimutic activity of Benzotriazole compound. In Control only vehicle is used that vehicle is distilled water and incubate all the petridishes at room temperature for 24 hrs. After getting the results of antimutic activity of Benzotriazole compound. we randomly selected 3 seeds from each and every petriplate and calculate the germination length in

cms of the seeds and after that we done average length calculation.

Accurately weight about 1gm of Benzotriazole drug from the synthesized product and dissolved in the distilled water then make up to 50ml with the distilled water in the Volumetric flask.

Preparation of Benzotriazole drug solution:

Figure.1: BZT Drug Solution

Figure.2: Green Gram Seeds

Table.5: Preparation of Antimitotic activity of Benzotriazole (BZT) compound.

S.no	Concentration of Benzotriazole compound (ml)	Contents in the petriplate
1	Control (0ml BZT)	10ml vehicle only

2	0.5ml (BZT)	10ml vehicle + 0.5ml BZT
3	1ml (BZT)	10mlvehicle +1ml BZT
4	1.5ml (BZT)	10mlvehicle + 1.5ml BZT
5	2ml (BZT)	10mlvehicle + 2ml BZT

Figure.3: Results of Antimitotic Assay method for Benzotriazole Drug solution

Table.6: Result of Antimitotic Activity of Benzotriazole compound.

S. No	Concentration of Benzotriazole compound (ML)	Length of seeds (cm)	Average length of the seeds(cm)
1	Control	First Seed- 4cm Second seed -4.5cm Third seed -4.5cm	$4+4.5+4.5= 13/3$ =4.3cms
2	0.5ml	First Seed- 2.5cm Second seed-3cm Third seed -3.7cm	$2.5+3+3.7 = 9.2/3$ = 3.06cms
3	1ml	First seed -1.5cm Second seed-2cm Third seed-2.5cm	$1.5+2+2.5= 6/3$ =2cms
4	1.5ml	First seed -0.9cm Second seed -0.5cm Third seed -0cm	$0.9+0.5+0 = 1.4/3$ = 0.46cms
5	2ml	First seed -0cm Second seed -0cm Third seed -0cm	No germination of seeds

From the Figure.3 We obtained the results of antimitotic activity from this we calculated the

average length of seeds germination from each and every individual concentrations of Benzotriazole

(BZT) drug solution. Then after we plot a graph for taking the Average length of seeds in Y-axis and concentration of Benzotriazole drug solution in X-Axis.

Figure.4: Graphical Representation of Antimitotic Assay of Benzotriazole Drug Solution

CONCLUSION:

From the Above results of Antimitotic activity of Benzotriazole (BZT) Drug solution we observe that there is a gradually reduction in Average length of the seeds. so we conclude that highest strength of the BZT drug solution is not having any seed germination from this it is conformed that the Benzotriazole Compound is having Antimitotic activity.

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HOW TO CITE: Satish Ponnada* Bhagyalaxmi Suvvari, Synthesis and Antimitotic Activity of Benzotriazole Compound, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 4, 2932-2937 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15273474>

